

STRUCTURES OF SMALL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

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INTRODUCTION

Based on the decisions, decrees and speeches of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the introduction of information, communication and modern pedagogical technologies into the educational system, today's advanced pedagogical technologies, information base resources and the increase in the need for software tools shows the urgency of its production and use in education. General concepts of database management systems, their types, classification, database models and forms of their standardization , the components of the languages working with the database and the technology of query organization, as well as information about the procedure for working with the knowledge base are presented. Students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges, as well as students of institutes and universities, are widely engaged in data processing on the basis of new information technologies using modern computers. Current in the day from the computer user each one person WORD text editor using texts again to work , that is necessary in appearance formatting , printing and one how much copy to receive without difficulty done increases . Calculations with depends issues Presentation in EXCEL processes in PowerPoint done increase to many known . Same as well as to internet pages information input from the HTML language for or from FrontPage use need you know Computer with depends and computer using very fast done increase possible has been so issues category they exist _ with each day and each in step it will happen . _ Such issues category data is called the base .

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Currently, the activities of various enterprises cannot be performed without an information system, which allows the automation of data collection and processing. A database was created to store and access data containing the required information.

The goal of any information system is to process information about the size of the real world. In a broad sense, a database is a collection of information about specific objects of the real world in any field. Under the subject area, it is

common for the real world (Enterprise or University) to be studied to organize control and automation.

The information model understands the information about the object selected and structured according to this purpose.

A data model is a way to define the types of logical structures in the database and to define and maintain the integrity of the database.

The first databases were created on the basis of file systems, and all responsibility for working with them was implemented in the software that used these databases. File databases are now deprecated. In modern database technology, database creation, its support and user access are centralized using special software tools - database management systems.

A database management system (DBTMS) is a set of programs and software designed to create, maintain and use a database of users.

Modern database servers include all kinds of changes and mechanisms for high-level interaction with the user. These development tools allow users to create applications that function as DBBMS.

ZBBMS is a software package that many people use to maintain these programs and use the results of their work.

Software includes all computer programs used to operate a database management system. Three types of software are required to perform all DBMS functions:

- 1) system software (controls all components of the equipment and provides access to all other programs running on the computer);
- 2) software DBMS (manages a database that implements DBMS functions);
- 3) software programs and utility programs (used to enter the environment and manage them in the environment, software programs are used to express the data stored in the database as reports and tables.

DBTS stands for Free Software Software.

If we take the basis of functional obligations, six main groups can be allocated to DBMM:

- 1) System administrators - responsible and responsible for providing reliable software
- 2) database administrators - present and manage the DBMM, create records, perform procedures related to the reliability of data storage (rights, restrictions, limitations, restrictions)
- 3) system analysts - perform work on the systematization of data structures, programs and reports

- 4) database designers - design design composition
- 5) Developers - development of application software
- 6) End users use application software to perform day-to-day operations.

The database includes:

- 1) data (all actual material stored in the database). Raw materials to be built
- 2) Metadata (the contents of the system directory). Provide information about tables, user rights, restrictions and other database objects
- 3) procedures are an important component of the system. Establishing standards of maintenance of commercial, technological and technical activities within the enterprise and interaction with customers

DBMM classification . By type of model received:

1) Hierarchical - relationships between database objects form an inverted tree, ie each main element of the hierarchy is connected with one element above it.

2) Network - communication between data objects can be established in any order

3) Schema - each piece of information in the database is identified by a table name, defined identifier and field name

4) There are object-oriented mechanisms for constructing data in the form of language extensions and software addresses across the core of objects that contain object-specific information.

5) object-oriented - based on a combination of three principles: Short model, standards for describing objects and principles, object-oriented programming

By architecture:

local databases (all data and objects on the same computer) and distribution (data and objects on different computers)

By accessing the database:

1) Film-Server - on each client's computer, and access to data is carried out through the local network.

2) client-server - providing coverage of access between user and network and use between machines.

3) installed - refers to the program library. Data is accessed by querying the SQL language or by calling application functions from the application

In terms of processing speed:

Operational (high speed to retrieve and provide information) and data warehouses (takes a lot of time because there are a lot of data bases)

The DBMS performs the following functions:

1) Data abstracts, dictionary management to search for the necessary data structures and their DBMS relations uses a data dictionary, avoiding coding of such complex relations in each program.

2) Data storage management - DBMS creates the complex structures required for data storage, freeing programmers from defining physical data properties and software

3) Data transformation and tariff - DBMS includes the task of transforming them into a form convenient for storage, inputting them to form and forming them. Ensuring data independence, the DBMS transforms logical queries into commands that specify their physical location and extraction

4) Security management - DBMS creates a security system in the database that ensures user protection and data privacy

5) Manage multiplayer access - DBMS creates complex structures that provide access to multiple users at the same time

6) Backup and recovery management - DBMS has a backup and data recovery procedure that ensures their safety and integrity.

7) Data integrity management - DBMS provides information that ensures data integrity, which allows data transfer and ensuring their consistency

8) Support for data entry and exit programs - DBMS provides access to data using a query language (necrotic language, ie).

9) database - the interface of interactions with the current generation, the database provides special collaboration programs that allow you to provide records in a network environment

It should be noted that modern database servers are often provided with a modeling tool for the "object-relationship" model or other means of creating data schemas.

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